

FACTORS INFLUENCING CUSTOMER'S USAGE INTENTION TOWARDS FOOD DELIVERY APPS IN GOA: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

The emergence of food delivery apps has changed the way the restaurant industry functioned traditionally. The aim of the study was to determine and analyze the factors affecting customers' usage intention towards food delivery apps in Goa with reference to the Covid-19 pandemic. The study encompasses the factors that influence the usage intention of consumers in the state of North Goa. A total of 232 valid questionnaires were collected using convenience sampling and empirically tested. During the study, the leading food delivery service providers in Goa were Swiggy and Zomato. This study seeks insights from The Technology Acceptance Model, The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Model and The Health Belief Model which have been extended with several factors to determine and analyze their influence on consumer usage intention. From the results, it was found that the factors that influence Goan customers the most are Trust, Time-Saving Benefits and Price-Saving Benefits whereas Food Safety Risk Perception and Perceived Vulnerability have a trivial influence on the same. Food delivery service apps have attracted an immense volume of customers due to the various benefits offered, like the availability of an array of food choices, doorstep delivery, shorter wait times etc. Therefore, it definitely has been a boon for consumers, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Keywords: Food Delivery App, Covid-19, Usage intention, Health Belief Model, Food Delivery Service

1. Introduction

Food delivery aided through digital apps has emerged as one of the fast-growing developments in the e-commerce space. The advent of digital tools has bestowed a different outlook on the food industry. Consumers today have the privilege to choose from various cuisines, from a range of food providers listed in the e-commerce space. Added attractions like no minimum order value and the multitude of payment options like net banking, digital wallets, and cash on delivery have increased consumer convenience. The shrinking urban-rural divide with easy access to smartphones has hastened the growth and acceptance of online food delivery systems. Companies have re-modelled their business strategies on a modern-day digital platform to keep pace with the customer's changing needs and preferences. (Thamaraiselvan et al., 2019)

The consumers have established delivery models existing in the market for the convenient delivery of food to them. Those are traditional models of delivery of food using telephone, website and text message. Whereas, Mobile application food delivery model, has been newly

established in India. Thus, creating an alternative option for the consumers to get the food delivered to their place. (Densingh Joshua Israel, 2020)

COVID-19 has taught the world a lot more than just how important hand washing is. The onset of the pandemic swiftly uprooted many industries and, with restaurants and bars forced to shut up shop to slow the spread of the virus, many had to swiftly adapt to in order to keep their heads above water. This often involved moving their business onto a food delivery app. As the world begins to make plans for a post-Covid-19 future, food retailers and manufacturers are increasingly looking to technological innovators to enable them to flourish in this constantly evolving landscape. (Palaniappan, 2020)

The state of Goa in India has the Arabian Sea flanking its west coast (Team TCG, 2020). Food and drinks are an integral part of marking Goa's vibrant culture (Sneha Virmani, n.d.). The unique cuisine of Goa developed out of a merger of various cultures that it came into contact with over the centuries such as the Portuguese, Arab, Brazilian, African, French, Konkani, Malabari, Malaysian and Chinese (Ministry of Culture, n.d.). This leads to Goans having a very diverse palette and are always on a quest to try new cuisines.

Until a few years ago, dining out and being waited on was considered a luxury that was exclusive to the wealthy (Shanti Maria Fonseca, 2012). Until the invention of the food delivery industry that revamped the dining trends and functionality of the given industry. According to (Sanyukta Kanwal, 2022) in the Statista 2022 report, Goans have a high standard of living leading to higher disposable income, which is seen in their enthusiasm to celebrate every occasion. This service gives them the convenience to order anywhere, at any time in spite of the delivery fee incurred.

Being the 11th most literate state in India with 88.70% average literacy (Goa Population Census 2011 | Goa Religion, Caste Data - Census 2011, 2022), people here are up to date with latest happenings in the country, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. Though there was a standstill in the online food delivery industry at the advent of the pandemic. Over time Goans fathomed the perks it brought with it. From offering a variety of food choices to taking utmost precaution by offering contactless delivery, this paved the way and stimulated the growth of online food delivery services in Goa.

This study aims to determine and assess the factors that predict customer's intent to use food delivery apps in the state of Goa. We also sought to ascertain whether the Covid-19 pandemic influenced the use behaviour of customers towards this service. The pattern Matrix calculated six reliable factors i.e. Customer Usage Intention, Food Safety Risk Perception, Trust, Time Saving Benefits, Perceived Vulnerability and Price Saving Benefits. These were extracted via exploratory factor analysis using maximum likelihood as the extraction method and using rotation method Varimax. It was further tested for reliability and suitable statistical tests were conducted to analyse the relationship between the variables.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Scope

The topic “Factors Influencing Customer’s Usage Intention towards Food Delivery Apps in Goa: An Empirical Study with Reference to the Covid-19 Pandemic”, encompasses the factors that influence the usage intention of consumers in the state of North Goa. The study emphasises the relationship between the factors that influence customer’s intention to use food delivery apps by drawing insights from the Technology Acceptance Model, The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Model and The Health Belief model.

2.2 Sources of Data Collection

Primary Research: For research work data was collected through a structured questionnaire from the respondents selected through convenience sampling technique.

Secondary Research: This data was procured from books, websites, research papers and e-articles.

2.3 Statistical Techniques

The analysis was done through SPSS 21 (Statistical Product and Service Solutions). Based on the type of data and measurement levels, appropriate statistical techniques were used to accomplish the objectives of the present study. The Descriptive Analysis was conducted to summarize the data obtained. The Pearson Correlation Analysis was done to study the relationship between the factors influencing usage intention towards food delivery apps. The Multiple Co linearity Test and Multiple Regression Analysis was carried out to examine the effect the factors have on customer’s usage intention towards food delivery apps.

2.4 Sample Size and Questionnaire Structure

The survey was undertaken for 232 respondents. A self-administered questionnaire was developed based on a comprehensive review of previous literature (Deepika, 2020; Hong et al., 2021). The first section of the questionnaire included questions asking the socio-demographic information of the respondents. The second section included items measuring study constructs, including Trust, Price Saving Benefits, Time Saving Benefits, Food Safety Risk Perception, Perceived Vulnerability and Customer Usage Intention using a 5-point Likert scale (1 being “strongly disagree”; 5 being “strongly agree”).

3. Research Aim

The aim of this study was to understand the factors that influence the customer’s usage intention towards food delivery apps in Goa and how the Covid-19 pandemic has affected the same thus leading to identifying the potential of food delivery apps and their acceptance among consumers.

4. Research Questions

1. What are the factors influencing the intention of Goan consumers to use food delivery apps?
2. Does the Covid-19 pandemic impact the intention of Goan consumers to use food delivery apps?

5. Objectives of the Study

1. To identify the factors that influence customer's intention to use food delivery apps.
2. To empirically examine the factors predicting customer's usage intention towards food delivery apps.

6. Research Gap

From the existing literature, it was found that there is little to no research conducted in this area in the state of Goa. To fill this gap, this research proposed to study the usage of food delivery apps among Goan consumers and analyse the same by seeking insights from various models and making use of statistical tools.

7. Limitations

1. This study only considered input from consumers. Future research on food delivery apps can consider restaurant owners, delivery personnel etc.
2. This study is limited only to North Goa. Future research can take South Goa as well into consideration.
3. The sample size is relatively small because of the awareness of food delivery apps is not as well-known as established restaurants, which made collection of data challenging.

8. Literature Review

Online Food Delivery services refer to internet-based food ordering and delivery systems that connect customers with partner restaurants via their websites or mobile applications (Puneet Kaur et al., 2021). Food Delivery Apps, as an emerging online-to-offline mobile technology, provide a channel between catering enterprises and customers by integrating online order and offline delivery services. FDAs can be categorised into two patterns (Arghya Ray et al., 2019). First, the restaurants themselves, such as KFC, Domino's and Pizzahut etc. Second, the third-party intermediary platforms, such as, Uber Eats, Zomato, Ele.me MeituanWaimai and Baidu Waimai, which are more popular and have been widely adopted in China (Minjung Roh & Kiwan Park, 2019).

The Health Belief Model was constructed to explain which beliefs should be targeted in communication campaigns to cause positive health behaviours. The model specifies that if individuals perceive a negative health outcome to be severe, perceive themselves to be susceptible to it, then the behaviour is likely for those individuals (Christopher J. Carpenter, 2010).

The Unified theory of use and acceptance of technology (UTAUT), as a reflection of social cognition theory, is an extension of the technology acceptance model developed by (Viswanath Venkatesh et al., 2003) for predicting users' behavioural intention to use new technology systems. Specifically, the UTAUT model has been modified with other factors and widely implemented on mobile technology adoption. (JalayerKhalilzadeh et al., 2017) modified UTAUT to verify that trust is associated with security and risk, and significantly affects customers' intentions to use mobile payment technology. Therefore, UTAUT as an advanced technology adoption model can be applied by associating additional variables or integrating with other models to explain the factors determining users' continuance intention of using FDAs during the COVID-19 pandemic efficiently (Yuyang Zhao & Fernando Bacao, 2020).

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) originally proposed by (Fred D. Davis & Fred Davis, 1989) states that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use of a new technology play significant roles in the adoption of the technology (Fred D. Davis et al., 1989). Researchers have explored various factors affecting customer usage intention towards food delivery apps. (MeeheeCho et al., 2019) identified system trust as significant predictor of customer usage intention (CUI) towards food delivery apps. (Arghya Ray & Pradip KumarBala, 2021) presented that price benefits, trust enhanced customer usage intention (CUI).

(Kiran Raj K. M. & Nandha Kumar K. G., 2021), coined that even though there was a slowdown in the market due to Covid-19 and the implementation of lockdown the online delivery services are progressing at a rapid rate. After loosening the lock-down the industry was growing back and there was an increase in demand for online food delivery services.

(Deepika, 2020), highlighted that comfort and convenience makes consumers more inclined towards online food ordering and different services given by application makes consumers happy and satisfied. They further concluded that due to urbanization in the Indian landscape, online food delivery applications are growing with flying colours and the future of online food ordering is bright.

Based on existing literature related to food delivery apps the following predictors determining customer usage intention towards food delivery apps were drawn:

Factors predicting Customer's Usage Intention towards Food Delivery Apps.

FSRP = Food Safety Risk Perception

The perceived risk associated with food consumption is called food safety risk perception (Vinicius Antonio Machado Nardi et al., 2020). When dining out, customers often do not possess the tools or skills to measure actual food safety. Instead, customers evaluate the cleanliness and food safety of the restaurant based on various aspects of the restaurant, including restaurant hygiene and employees' safety practices of wearing clean uniforms and sanitary gloves while touching food (Pei Liu & Yee Ming Lee, 2018). Food delivery services are challenged to sustain food safety and hygiene because food delivered through online food delivery services can also be exposed to contamination due to the addition of delivery processes to the traditional restaurant business model. Specifically, controlling temperature, packaging,

and using appropriate food containers during the delivery process are additional concerns with food delivery services (MayilaMaimaiti et al., 2018).

TR = Trust

Trust refers to an index of a positive belief regarding the perceived reliability, dependence, and assurance in an individual, object, or procedure (BJ Fogg & Hsiang Tseng, 1999). Trust in the system has been validated as a key driver in adopting new technology in various disciplines from self-service kiosks during check-in/out in hotels (Arun Kumar Kaushik et al., 2015) to electronic payments (Julio C. Mendoza-Tello et al., 2018). Several studies have agreed that TR is one of the most critical factors positively affecting CUI (Arghya Ray & Pradip Kumar Bala, 2021; Meehee Cho et al., 2019) (Yuyang Zhao & Fernando Bacao, 2020).

TSB = Time Saving Benefits

Food delivery services could save customers time by avoiding the time spent travelling to a restaurant and waiting in line. Moreover, many web browsers and food delivery apps allow customers to store payment and previous order details for efficient checkout, enabling customers to save time (Akshat Bansal, 2019; Statista EServices Report 2020, 2020). In other words, when customers believe they can avoid traffic and save time by using food delivery services, they are more likely to use food delivery services (Hong et al., 2021).

PV = Perceived Vulnerability

Perceived Vulnerability refers to personal belief(s) regarding the risk of getting a disease (Ignatius Cahyanto et al., 2016). The Health Belief Model explains that when people have higher perceived vulnerability to an adverse health condition and such outcomes, individuals are more likely to take actions that reduce the threat (Christopher J. Carpenter, 2010).

PSB = Price Saving Benefits

This study examines price-saving benefits as a critical predictor of customer usage intention. Price-saving benefits are defined as money-saving benefits as well as not charging any additional costs for purchasing products/services (Vincent Cheow Sern Yeo et al., 2017). In Food Delivery service setting, price saving promotions often serve as effective marketing tools as confirmed by (Puneet Kaur et al., 2021) as well as (Arghya Ray & Pradip Kumar Bala, 2021) who revealed that free delivery, lower delivery fees, or promotional incentives enhance customer usage intention.

9. Data Analysis

9.1 KMO and Bartlett's test

Table 1

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.883
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2823.484
	df	253
	Sig.	.000

The adequacy of the sample is measured by KMO in SPSS (Noor UIHadi et al., 2016). It is a statistic that indicates the proportion of variance in your variables that might be caused by underlying factors. KMO returns values between 0 and 1. High values (close to 1.0) generally indicate that a factor analysis may be useful with your data. If the value is less than 0.50, the results of the factor analysis probably won't be very useful (IBM Corporation, 2021). Kaiser (1974) recommends a bare minimum of 0.5 and the value between 0.5 and 0.7 are mediocre, value between 0.7 and 0.8 are good, value between 0.8 and 0.9 are great and value between 0.9 and above are superb (Graeme D Hutcheson & Nick Sofroniou, 1999). In this study we have got the result of 0.883 which is a great result.

9.2 Pattern Matrix

Table 2

	Factors					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Customer Usage Intention 2	.836					
Customer Usage Intention 3	.827					
Customer Usage Intention 4	.771					
Customer Usage Intention 5	.586					
Customer Usage Intention 1	.578					
Food Safety Risk Perception 3		.838				
Food Safety Risk Perception 4		.749				
Food Safety Risk Perception 2		.748				
Food Safety Risk Perception 5		.713				
Food Safety Risk Perception 1		.544				
Trust 2			.902			
Trust 1			.863			
Trust 3			.834			
Time Saving Benefits 1				.831		
Time Saving Benefits 2				.825		
Time Saving Benefits 3				.710		
Perceived Vulnerability 2					.769	
Perceived Vulnerability 1					.767	
Price Saving Benefits 1						.735
Price Saving Benefits 2						.678
Price Saving Benefits 3						.590

Exploratory factor analysis is a statistical technique that is used to reduce data to a smaller set of summary variables and to identify the structure of the relationship between the variable and the respondent. VARIMAX is used to simplify the column of the factor matrix so that the factor extracts are clearly associated and there should be some separation among the variables. Factor

loading can be classified based on their magnitude: Greater than + .30 — minimum consideration level + .40 — more important + .50 — practically significant. (Statistics Solutions, n.d.)

The pattern Matrix calculated 6 reliable factors i.e. Customer Usage Intention, Food Safety Risk Perception, Trust, Time Saving Benefits, Perceived Vulnerability and Price Saving Benefits got extracted from exploratory factor analysis using maximum likelihood as the extraction method and using rotation method Varimax. These factors were further tested for their reliability. All the values here were above .50 which is practically significant.

9.3 Reliability test

Table 3

	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Customer Usage Intention	.846	5
Food Safety Risk Perception	.770	5
Trust	.929	3
Time Saving Benefits	.815	3
Perceived Vulnerability	.786	2
Price Saving Benefits	.654	3

Cronbach's Alpha is a way to measure the internal consistency of a questionnaire or survey. Cronbach's Alpha ranges between 0 and 1, with higher values indicating that the survey or questionnaire is more reliable. Values below 0.5= Unacceptable, 0.5-0.6= Poor, 0.6-0.7=Questionable, 0.7-0.8= Acceptable, 0.8-0.9=Good and Above 0.9= Excellent.(ZACH, 2021)

Using reliability statistics, we have arrived at having 0.9 for Trust followed by Customer Usage Intention and Time Saving Benefits with 0.8, Food Safety Risk Perception and Perceived Vulnerability with 0.7 and Price Saving Benefits with 0.6 which are all acceptable having adequate internal consistency.

9.4 Descriptive Analysis of Factors

Table 4

Factors	Mean	SD
Food Safety Risk Perception	2.86	.699
Trust	3.91	.714
Time Saving Benefits	3.88	.642
Perceived Vulnerability	2.91	.922
Price Saving Benefits	3.68	.971

Trust is considered as the most important factor (3.91) in determining the usage intention towards food delivery apps, followed by Time Saving Benefits (3.88) and Price Saving Benefits (3.68). The least important factors are Food Safety Risk Perception (2.86) which shows risk associated with food consumption, controlling temperature, packaging, and using appropriate food containers during the delivery and Perceived Vulnerability (2.91) which involves the risk associated with catching the virus. The SD indices in all instances are within acceptable limits of ± 2 (Frederick J Gravetter & Larry B. Wallnau, 1991).

9.5 Pearson Correlation Analysis

Table 5

	FSRP	TR	TSB	PV	PSB	CUI
FSRP	1.000					
TR	-.162*	1.000				
TSB	-.079	.356**	1.000			
PV	-.084	.284**	.219**	1.000		
PSB	-.114	.339**	.489**	.311**	1.000	
CUI	-.135*	.502**	.493**	.226**	.454**	1.000

Note: ** denotes significant at 1% level.

* denotes significant at 5% level.

The above table indicates correlation coefficients among all the constructs where most of the correlations are significant at $p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$. Correlation coefficients measure the strength of the relationship between two variables (Philip Bobko, 2001). All the independent variables, were positively correlated with the dependent variable, Customer Usage Intention except Food Safety Risk Perception its value being ($r = -.135$). Trust had the highest correlation ($r = .502$) at $p < .01$. Perceived Vulnerability had the lowest correlation with Customer Usage Intention ($r = .226$) at $p < .01$.

Correlation can take any value from -1 to 1. The negative sign indicates a negative correlation while positive sign a positive correlation and 0 indicates no correlation (Paul Andrew Watters & Sarah Boslaugh, 2008). From the results we can interpret that a change in Food Safety Risk Perception ($-.135^2 = 0.02$) will have an inverse effect on Customer Usage Intention. A change in Trust, Time Saving Benefits and Price Saving Benefits on the other hand will have a significantly direct effect on Customer Usage Intention values being ($.502^2 = 0.25$), ($.493^2 = 0.24$) and ($.454^2 = 0.21$) respectively. While a change in Perceived Vulnerability ($.226^2 = 0.05$) will have a minor effect on Customer Usage Intention.

From the above results we can therefore conclude that, Trust, Time Saving Benefits and Price Saving Benefits are very important factors and have a substantial influence on Customer's Usage Intention towards food delivery apps where as Food Safety Risk Perception and Perceived Vulnerability have a trivial influence towards the same.

9.6 Multiple Collinearity Test

Table 6

Independent Variables	Tolerance	VIF
Food Safety Risk Perception	.969	1.032
Trust	.796	1.256
Time Saving Benefits	.719	1.391
Perceived Vulnerability	.866	1.155
Price Saving Benefits	.697	1.434

According to (Joseph F. Hair et al., 2019) the estimated path coefficients can be affected if the independent variables are highly correlated among themselves. Multicollinearity can be detected through the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance level. The recommended threshold for variance inflation factor (VIF) is below 5 and tolerance is above 0.10 (Joseph F. Hair et al., 2019) Here, the maximum VIF is 1.434 and in an acceptable level. Tolerance value also falls within the acceptable range (0.10 and 1). So, multiple regression analysis is appropriate for analysing the data.

9.7 Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 7

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable	Adj. R ²	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Sig.	Impact
FSRP	Customer Usage Intention	.384	-.037	-.698	.486	Insignificant
TR			.328	5.665	.000	Significant
TSB			.272	4.465	.000	Significant
PV			.007	.124	.901	Insignificant
PSB			.204	3.300	.001	Significant

Multiple Regression analysis helps in determining how strongly affiliated one dependent variable is to a series of changing independent variables. Specifically, regression analysis helps us determine which factors count most and which we can overlook.

The above multiple regression analysis indicates that three out of five independent variables were significantly related Customer Usage Intention. Food Safety Risk Perception and Perceived Vulnerability had no significant relationship with Customer Usage Intention. Food Safety Risk Perception (Beta=-.037, t=-.698) and Perceived Vulnerability (Beta=.007, t=.124)

are insignificantly related to Customer usage intention at $p > 0.05$. Through this we can imply that Trust, Time Saving Benefits and Price Saving Benefits are the dominant factors influencing consumers to use food delivery apps while Food Safety Risk Perception and Perceived Vulnerability do not have much of an effect on the same.

The relationship is further supported by coefficient of determination or R^2 value (0.384) which implies that around 38.4% variance of customer usage intention is explained by all the independent variables. A higher value of R^2 indicates a better prediction of dependent variable. According to (Joseph F. Hair et al., 2019), R^2 values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 indicates substantial, moderate, and weak, respectively. As illustrated in the table, The R^2 value of 0.384 shows a close to moderate effect of all the independent variables on dependent variable.

10. Conclusion

This research analysed the factors to provide insights that would enable food delivery service providers to retain customers and their position in the immensely competitive marketplace. The factors that influence Goancustomers the most to use food delivery apps are trust, time-saving benefits and price-saving benefits. With the inception of the pandemic, most operations went online. Customers started using e-payment mediums while ordering food online and this signified their trust in the service. Customers are motivated when the apps offer discounts and cash backs which in turn gives them value for money. Food delivery apps offer a variety of features one being its time and location tracking feature which gives the customer the delivery time estimate of their orders and hence provides clarity on the same.

Even with the fear associated with catching the virus, customers continued to use this service because of their trust in the food delivery app companies, who ensured that the delivery riders were vaccinated and appropriate sanitation measures were taken through packaging and contactless delivery. The convenience offered by food delivery apps during the pandemic gained the loyalty and trust of several users and hence is expected to see future growth prospects if it keeps improving its innovation and continued focus on customer satisfaction.

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